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**LIVING IN TWO WORLDS: A DOCUMENTARY ON BALANCING LIFE WITH AN
AUTISTIC CHILD**

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31 August 2024

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **ANGELA MARIE S. LUMAGUIP** with the title: “**LIVING IN TWO WORLDS: A DOCUMENTARY ON BALANCING LIFE WITH AN AUTISTIC CHILD**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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ABSTRACT

“Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child” is a video documentary that tells the stories of four (4) Filipino mothers as they navigate their daily lives, careers, and roles as parents to children diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). In this documentary video, they discuss their personal experiences upon noticing their children’s signs or symptoms and how they were diagnosed. They also share their initial questions and concerns, how they came to accept the situation, the interventions their children undergo, their children's unique traits, advice for fellow parents, ways to educate the public, and the challenges they face during interventions, in educational settings, and social situations. The rationale behind this video is the lack of documentaries about ASD in the Philippines. It aims to raise societal awareness, promote inclusivity, and empower individuals with ASD—children and adults alike.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD); Autism; Documentary Video; Parents with Autistic Children

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

Background

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) encompasses a broad spectrum of neurodevelopmental disorders that affect a person's capacity to communicate and interact with their surroundings and can be detected as early as the age of three. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) conducted a study indicating a higher frequency of ASD among male children than females in the United States, with genetic and environmental factors playing a significant role (Zaky, 2017). While the ASD population continues to rise, the specific cause and cure for ASD are still unknown.

The Autism Society Philippines (n.d.) stated that one in every 100 Filipinos has ASD, representing a total of around 1.2 million people in the Philippines. However, only about 15,000 individuals with autism are recorded to have Persons With Disabilities (PWD) IDs from 2017 to 2023 (Statistics of Children With Autism Spectrum Disorder, n.d.). Recently, Torregoza (2023) reported that the increase in the ASD population urged senators to pass a bill to fund the establishment of the country's first Center for Autism that caters to the needs of the ASD community in receiving proper treatment and to provide financial assistance to the families. Despite these efforts and several awareness campaigns, stigma and discrimination against people on the spectrum continue to persist in the Philippines.

After Michelle Dee, Miss Universe Philippines 2023, secured a gold award in the "Voice for Change" category (advocating for autism awareness), there has been increased attention and recognition for the ASD community (Serquiña, 2023). Nevertheless, many people remain uninformed about the symptoms and challenges

faced by individuals with ASD, as well as the issues and challenges experienced by their family members. Stereotypes, misconceptions, and stigma in society contribute to discrimination against the ASD community, perpetuating myths associating ASD with poor parenting, vaccines, hostility, and a lack of empathy (Gutierrez, 2024). Individuals with ASD are often unfairly judged when others perceive them as violent when they experience autistic meltdowns due to their communication difficulties.

Numerous studies, including those by Lasco et al. (2022) and Catubigan (2023), have shown that parents of autistic children struggle with daily challenges encompassing medical, financial, educational, and social aspects. Ilias et al. (2018) mentioned other factors, such as the severity of autism, views on ASD, and concern about the future of their children, that influence the stress that parents of children with ASD experience when raising their children.

Despite the efforts of films like *In His Mother's Eyes* (2023) and Netflix's "*Keys to the Heart*" (2023) aimed at increasing awareness of autism in the Philippines, there remains a lack of accurate media representation of ASD. Prochnow (2014) has noted that some films depicting ASD tend to romanticize or oversimplify autistic symptoms, and it is rare to find autistic actors portraying characters with autism. Instead of shedding light on the ASD communities, these portrayals often contribute to stigma by presenting stereotypical characters. On the other hand, documentary films offer a window into real-life experiences, serving as a means to raise awareness and convey a meaningful message (Jaafar et al., 2022). While there are documentary films on autism that mainly focus on parents with ASD children from other countries (Real Stories, 2021; CNA Insider, 2022), few are produced within the Philippines.

Objectives of the Special Project

The video documentary aims to:

- Raise awareness among parents who are in the early stages of discovering and understanding their child's condition.
- Present the real-life challenges of families with family member/s diagnosed with ASD.
- Debunk myths or misconceptions about ASD.
- Mitigate the public stigma and discrimination associated with ASD.
- Promote inclusivity and ASD empowerment by disseminating and sharing the output or content material to various social media platforms.

Significance of the Special Project

The ASD lacks accurate media representation in the Philippines. Although there are relatable vlogs from famous Filipino personalities with autistic children, such as Candy Pangilinan, Karen Davila, and Troy and Aubrey Miller (Pasimio, 2023), ordinary parents seem to lack representation. Through this documentary film, the study aims to portray parents coping with a child diagnosed with ASD.

The documentary film also aims to promote inclusivity and awareness in society by maximizing the use of social media and disseminating the output to various platforms. Disrupting stigma, misconceptions, and discrimination associated with the ASD community while incorporating different parents of children with ASD perspectives' would help people understand the spectrum better.

Scopes and Limitations of the Special Project

The video features only four (4) interviewees, all parents of children with ASD, who reside within Metro Manila. It should be emphasized that the parents interviewed in the documentary video do not represent the entire ASD population as it has a broad spectrum with different cases in every diagnosis. It does not assume similar experiences among all families dealing with ASD. Each parent employs their own coping methods, which vary based on their individual circumstances.

It should also be noted with a disclaimer that the documentary film does not intend to spread false information in case the interviewees provide answers that could mislead viewers. The interviewees' responses are based on their personal experiences and beliefs and do not represent all parents of children diagnosed with ASD. For future works or documentaries on similar topics, consulting a professional with expertise in ASD is recommended.

CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Media Representation of ASD in TV and Films

Depicting social issues through popular media made it easier for viewers to be aware, educated, and entertained at the same time. This case similarly applies to raising awareness by portraying ASD characters in the media. Due to the rise of character portrayals of ASD in films and television, numerous studies have focused on the media representations of ASD and its impact on the viewers.

Dean & Nordahl-Hansen (2021) reviewed the current status of character portrayals of ASD across various TV shows and films worldwide. The researchers emphasized ongoing efforts to showcase ASD representations in diverse cultural contexts with nearly a balanced representation of both male and female characters with ASD. However, the study showed that there is a lack of media representation of minority groups, characters' SOGIE, and seniors with ASD. Furthermore, the majority of characters discussed in the reviewed articles were characterized as white/Caucasian, potentially reinforcing stereotypes in society (Pronchow, 2014). Aside from the stereotypical race, it was also mentioned in a similar study (Nordahl-Hansen et al., 2017) where *Rain Man (1988)* was cited as an example that savantism is always associated with ASD, which may cause inaccurate representation and misconception of ASD. Although there are no studies found in the context of the Philippines, the identified gap of these studies suggests the impact of these character portrayals of ASD in media on the viewers.

To explore the impact of media representations of ASD further, Jones (2022) conducted a study examining the perspectives of 29 individuals with autism regarding the representation of ASD in entertainment media. The findings indicate a demand for

a more significant presence of diverse, accurate, and positive portrayals of characters with autism in entertainment media. Moreover, the participants prefer authentic representation with actual autistic actors portraying characters with ASD in the media. Conversely, in a related study focusing on attitudes toward autistic stereotypes, recent research explored the impact of video clips involving neurotypical individuals (Mallipeddi et al., 2024). The study revealed that participants favor informational videos that involve an autistic character portrayed by an autistic actress who shares their experiences as part of ASD. On the other hand, Orm et al. (2023) present recommendations for improving the media portrayal of ASD in TV and films by incorporating autistic writers, consultants, and actors to promote inclusivity and diversity in the media industry.

The portrayal of ASD in television and movies carries both positive and negative implications. On the positive side, it has the potential to raise awareness and foster inclusivity within ASD communities. However, such representation might also lead to societal stigma and present inaccurate depictions of individuals with ASD.

Documentaries on ASD

Although biases or limitations are still evident in documentaries, Prochnow (2014) indicates they provide more realistic representations of ASD than TV and films since they feature non-fictional characters in authentic and real-life situations. Cavalcante et al. (2016) stated that documentaries offer a glimpse into the challenges and experiences of the subjects involved, potentially leading to a shift in viewers' perspectives and fostering empathy for the individuals featured. However, the availability of published studies or scientific journal articles specifically addressing documentaries centered on parents with ASD children or individuals with ASD appears

to be limited. Some documentaries are accessible on video streaming platforms like YouTube (Real Stories, 2021; CNA Insider, 2022), yet others have restricted access to public viewing (Jaafar et al., 2022; Shaughnessy & Turner, 2016).

Released in 2003 but uploaded only three years ago, “Refrigerator Mothers” (Real Stories, 2021) delves into the challenges faced by mothers with ASD children during the era of the “Refrigerator Mother Theory.” This theory by Leo Kanner wrongly attributed blame to mothers for their children’s autism when seeking professional help in the 1950s to 1960s. Meanwhile, CNA’s documentary, *How We Live With Autism: Our Special Needs & Strengths* (CNA Insider, 2022), follows the experiences of two Singaporean mothers with children diagnosed with ASD. While this documentary does not represent all individuals with autism, the mothers’ observations align with the findings of studies by Pronchow (2014) and Catubigan (2023).

Another documentary, *Autism Every Day* (2006) by Lauren Thierry (Milestone VideoNY, 2011), explores the distressing notion of a mother contemplating harming her autistic child. This film received mixed reactions and substantial criticism (Bazile, 2019; daVanport, 2020; Evans, 2020).

In the Philippine context, only a few documentaries address ASD. *Alyana* (2006) by Mirana Medina is the first documentary film in the country aimed at raising awareness and dispelling myths about autism (Autism Society Philippines, 2008). Another significant documentary, *Lila: A Documentary on a Mother Raising a Child with Autism* (Ustaris, 2014), produced as a master’s thesis by a UP student, offers a maternal perspective on the challenges of raising a child with autism.

Current Studies on ASD in the Philippines

Lasco et al. (2022) study focused on the challenges in various aspects faced by parents of children with disabilities, including autism, specifically those from the cities of Davao and Tagum. Results showed that parents with autistic children were in denial at first but accepted the diagnosis eventually. Some doubted their religious beliefs, while others considered it as a blessing.

Another study conducted by Catubigan (2023) explored pre- and post-diagnosis experiences but specifically focused on a minority group in Mindanao, the Mansaka mothers. The same reactions were elicited by the Mansaka mothers when their children were diagnosed with ASD. Fears about their children's future and potential discrimination were prevalent, yet the Mansaka mothers focused more on understanding their children's condition and seeking professional assistance rather than doubting their faith.

Shifting the focus to a different perspective, Leosala (2023) delves into the experiences of Filipino parents with children on the autism spectrum who are undergoing early childhood intervention. While it does touch on the parents' journey from denial to acceptance following their children's diagnosis, the study highlights the impact of early intervention services. Parents expressed satisfaction with the services provided by teachers and therapists. While early intervention brought beneficial effects, parents continued to struggle with employment and financial challenges.

On a related note, Quilendrino et al. (2022) investigated the financial impact of caring for children diagnosed with ASD. The study revealed that the costs associated with healthcare, including education, therapies, medications, and consultations for individuals with ASD, amounted to an average total of ₱38,000 per year or ₱3,000 per

month, which consumes a significant percentage of the monthly income of a minimum-wage worker. Consequently, there is an urgent call for the government to provide financial assistance. Subsidies are needed to alleviate the financial burden faced by families with ASD children.

While there are numerous studies on the lived experiences of parents with children on the autism spectrum, research indicates a scarcity or absence of documentaries produced in the Philippines, even within the field of broadcast documentaries. Although a few videos or documentaries have been produced, these are currently inaccessible to the general public. It can also be noticed that these documentaries primarily centered around mothers' narratives. The current study, in contrast, aims to include perspectives from other genders raising children diagnosed with ASD.

CHAPTER III: THE VIDEO DOCUMENTARY PRODUCTION PROCESS

This chapter discusses the extensive process of making the video documentary successful, from planning (pre-production) to executing or filming (production) to editing and revising (post-production). A few changes from the original proposal were applied to make the production feasible and meet the expected time frame for production.

a. Pre-production

The interviewer/producer began by researching and creating an outline with a series of questions for the interview to gather relevant information and insights from the participants. Filipino is the primary language used throughout the interview, with optional English subtitles in closed captions (CC) to make the content accessible to non-Filipino-speaking individuals and foreign nationals.

While developing the interview questions and drafting the video documentary outline, the interviewer identified parents of children diagnosed with ASD residing within Metro Manila who were willing to be interviewed for the video through Autism group communities via Facebook. The interviewer specifically joined Autism PH, which has approximately 41,000 members, and Autism Community Philippines, which has an estimated 62,500 members, to reach out to those parents interested in being interviewed.

Figure 1. Autism PH Facebook Group

Figure 2. Autism Community Philippines Facebook Group

A preliminary survey via Google Forms (See APPENDIX A) was created to help choose four (4) interviewees willing to share their experiences since their location and availability are the top priorities in consideration. To attract more attention to the search for interviewees, the interviewer used Canva, an online open-source graphic design platform, in producing publication materials and specified four (4) qualifications to filter respondents easily:

- (1) working parent/s with a child diagnosed with ASD;
- (2) residing within Metro Manila;
- (3) willing to be interviewed in person, and;
- (4) child is currently undergoing early interventions/therapies

Initially, the interviewer intended to post “Call for Interviewees!” publication materials inside the group communities mentioned. Unfortunately, the posts did not gain traction after a week since they needed to be reviewed and accepted by the group administrators first. Due to the number of members’ posts needing to be reviewed daily, the posts might have been overlooked, which led the interviewer to reach out to the group chats feature instead.

Figure 3. “Call for Interviewees!” Publication Material

The interviewer was only able to gather six (6) responses: two (2) from Autism PH and four (4) from Autism Community Philippines, all of whom resided within Metro Manila. However, due to the unavailability of some respondents, only two interviewees tapped, one from Autism PH and one from Autism Community PH.

Aside from selecting interviewees from a social media platform, the interviewer also reached out to a family member, specifically her aunt, who has a child diagnosed with ASD. To complete the four (4) interviewees, the interviewer also asked her aunt to refer someone qualified and willing to be interviewed for the video documentary. She recommended a fellow parent, the mother of her child’s classmate, at the SpEd (Special Education) school. Despite not qualifying for the fourth requirement, where her child is not receiving any interventions or therapies, the interviewer still chose to include her story since some viewers may be able to relate to her experiences.

Searching and communicating with interviewees were conducted throughout April to May 2024. After contacting each willing interviewee, the interviewer asked for their availability and location and was presented with an outline of the documentary film (See APPENDIX B) and a consent form (See APPENDIX C). Calendly, an online scheduling tool, was utilized to check the availability of the selected interviewees. However, only the second interviewee responded through the platform, while the others proposed specific dates during the conversation instead.

Figure 4. Calendly’s Booking Page

b. Production

The video shoots lasted for two months, from June to July 2024. The on-camera interviews took place in areas near the interviewees' location, in Valenzuela, Manila, and Quezon City.

All consent forms were signed on the day of the shoot. Recording of the interviews on video only commenced after the interviewees had signed the consent. Montage shots of the children were also recorded after the parents consented. Recording and presenting of children diagnosed with ASD on video followed the approved policies indicated in the Guide For Media Practitioners On The Reporting And Coverage Of Cases Involving Children (Department of Justice, 2008) and the Philippine Press Institute's Guidelines in Reporting on Children (Philippine Press Institute, 2017).

The equipment used to film the interviewees was a Canon 200D DSLR camera with a kit lens (18-55mm), a tripod, and a BOYA BY-M1 Lavalier microphone. All the questions were based on the outline of the documentary film given to the interviewees before the interview.

The first interview was with the interviewer's aunt, who inspired her to create a video documentary about the parents' experiences with children diagnosed with ASD. In terms of technical aspects, unlike the other interviews conducted, the first interview did not have technical glitches or challenges.

Since the interviewer needed assistance conducting the second interview, she sought assistance from her UPOU friends/classmates who lived nearby to accompany her. Aside from setting up the equipment, the interviewer's friends talked and played

with the interviewee's children. Despite the unexpected cuts during the interview, since there was no room or an area where we could set up and conduct the interview in a quiet environment, the interview was still successful.

Figure 5. Second Interviewee's Facebook Post with UPOU Peers

For the third interview session, the interviewer rented a coworking space where the interview was conducted since the interviewee could not accommodate the interviewer at her home. Since it was a coworking space, there was a time when the receptionist knocked at the door to give a printed reminder in the middle of the interview, which almost affected the recording. Fortunately, the interviewee finished answering the question before the receptionist's knock was audible in the video.

Figure 6. Photo with Third Interviewee

The fourth interview session was with the friend of the interviewer's aunt. It was also conducted in the house of the first interviewee. The interview was recorded a day before super typhoon Carina brought heavy rainfall, causing concern due to the loud raindrops audible in the background.

Allowing the interviewees to share their stories gave the interviewer valuable insights despite not knowing them personally, except for her aunt. Each parent faces unique struggles and employs individual coping strategies to help, guide, teach, and meet their children's needs.

c. Post-production

After gathering all the necessary scenes for the interview, the documentary was edited for the whole month of August 2024. Initially, the target duration of the video documentary ranged from fifteen (15) to twenty (20) minutes. However, due to unforeseen circumstances, the final output lasted longer than the established time

frame based on the video documentary outline. The software application used to edit the videos was Adobe Premiere Pro.

Each interview, including the videos, footage, and audio recordings, was nested to combine multiple clips into a single clip for easier editing. This feature makes editing convenient by keeping the timeline clean and allowing editors to rename the nested clips for quick identification and tracking.

Figure 7. Nested Clips on the Timeline

The sequence of the clips followed the video documentary outline, though some adjustments were made to ensure the video looked neat and consistent. The title screen was changed from “4 Families, 4 Different Perspectives” to “Four Parents, Four Perspectives.” This change made each word start with the letter “P,” creating a more cohesive and memorable title (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Changes Made in the Title Screen

Figure 9. Title Screen

The order of the interviewees was also changed, with the second and third interviews swapping places to create an alternating visual effect of the interviewees looking in different directions. Montage shots of their children were also included in the middle of their interviews.

The suitable background music for the documentary was chosen from YouTube, following considerations such as copyright-free and royalty-free music. Audacity, a free audio editor software application, was also used to edit and trim the audio to fit the title screen better (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Unedited and Edited Audio of the Background Music Used

Figure 11. Edited Audio in Adobe Premiere Pro

The four (4) interviewees' self-introductions – giving their names, occupations, and children's ages, were included after the title screen. The interview was structured into segments based on each question, with the answers from all four (4) interviewees combined rather than having each interviewee respond to all questions individually. This format allows viewers to distinguish each interviewee's responses and highlight the differences in each parent's perspective. Background music was omitted during the interviews to ensure viewers could hear and fully concentrate on the respondents' answers.

One of the technical challenges encountered during editing was loud background noises. The first interview had no technical problems, yet the only concern was using unnecessary filler words or interjections. Although this case is not inevitable during interviews, some interjections were removed or edited to make the first interviewee's thoughts more coherent and understandable.

On the contrary, the second interviewee has the most noticeable background noise. Since their house is in an apartment complex with neighboring units separated by thin walls, the sounds from the neighbors were quite loud in the video. It was also amplified by the interviewee's children watching videos on their phones. DeHummer, a noise-reduction tool in Adobe Premiere Pro, was applied to eliminate the loud bass from outdoor sounds with a 40% harmonic frequency. The frequency was adjusted to 20 Hz to remove the bass without affecting the voice, keeping it sound natural (Figure 12). Applying additional noise reduction to the clips is not recommended, as it could cause the interviewee's voice to become uneven and distorted.

Figure 12. Applied DeHummer Effect to the Second Interview

Meanwhile, the third interviewee also faced audio issues with minimal background noise. The lavalier microphone was placed on her lap instead of being clipped inside her top garment, resulting in slightly muffled audio. Towards the end of the recording, specifically during the last two questions, the audio from the lavalier microphone became completely muffled because her child sat on her lap where the microphone was placed. Due to this issue, the audio from the camera was used instead. DeReverb, a noise-reduction audio effect in Adobe Premiere Pro, was applied

with an amount of 35% to help eliminate echoes from the room (Figure 13). Despite capturing some of her child’s clapping and tapping on the table and nearly recording the receptionist’s knock, as mentioned earlier, the coworking space still provided a generally quiet environment.

Figure 13. Applied DeReverb Effect on the End of Third Interviewee’s Answers

The fourth interview happened a day before super typhoon Carina hit the country. Heavy rains during the interview caused background noise in the audio. In addition to the rainfall, phone ringtones, faint voices, and dog barks were also recorded. Fortunately, using a lavalier microphone still helped reduce the capture of background noises.

After showing all the interviews, information in text format followed, which reminded viewers that the exact cause of ASD is still unknown and that autism is not something to be cured but a part of a child with ASD’s identity that needs to be accepted and embraced. Dr. Stephen Shore's quote, “If you’ve met a person with Autism, you’ve met a person with Autism,” and the autism rainbow infinity symbol were also added after the reminder. This quote and symbol highlight the diversity of people on the autism spectrum, emphasizing that each person is unique. This scene was followed by the video documentary’s title, the content creator’s identity, her

acknowledgment of the people behind the video documentary production, the places where the documentary was recorded, and acknowledgments of other materials used in the output, i.e., music pieces.

While reviewing and polishing the video further, the entire output was played while transcribing each word in a word processor program (Figure 14). The process was done in Microsoft Word, so there would already be a prepared copy when editing the timing for the subtitles when posted publicly or specifically on YouTube.

Figure 14. Transcription Process in Microsoft Word

The transcription process took a long time to accomplish. Optional English subtitles in closed captions (CC) were added, translating Filipino to English to make the video accessible to non-Filipino-speaking individuals and foreign nationals. Additionally, the main subtitles included translating the English text in the video to Filipino, ensuring inclusivity for all Filipino viewers.

The whole video is 51 minutes and 41 seconds long. The most crucial part was the rendering of the video project file to a format compatible with various video player apps, which took twelve (12) hours, from 11 AM to 11 PM. After rendering, the output was uploaded on YouTube to make it accessible to the public.

CHAPTER IV:

LESSONS LEARNED AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a content creator and video documentary producer, embarking on this journey provided valuable lessons that will be greatly treasured. It not only deepened the understanding of the topic and its impact on other people's lives, but it also revealed the challenges and huge responsibilities of being a content creator.

5.1. Pre-production

The pre-production phase involved researching Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), writing the documentary video outline, and selecting willing interviewees.

5.1.1. Planning and Research

Relevant studies and documentaries were gathered as a basis for writing the documentary video outline. The video documentary producer also considered the questions to be asked in the interview based on her personal experiences with her cousin, who was diagnosed with ASD.

The documentary outline included the objectives, output flow, and interview questions during the scriptwriting stage. The vision was to begin with statistics on Filipinos diagnosed with ASD, as reported by the Autism Society Philippines, to contextualize the documentary video within the Philippines.

After writing the documentary outline, the video documentary producer contacted an organization to help her gather and select willing interviewees. She also hoped to invite a professional with expertise in ASD to enhance the credibility of the documentary video. However, challenges were identified.

Nevertheless, reaching out through online group communities made it easier for the video documentary producer to gather her interviewees. Contacting them was relatively easy since they often use the platform to connect with fellow parents. She allowed them one to two months to choose a suitable interview schedule and shared the documentary outline with them in preparation for the interview.

5.1.2. Challenges

- Visualizing the video's flow was a bit difficult, especially considering the likelihood of numerous modifications during production and post-production.
- Initially, the plan was to coordinate with an organization dedicated to helping individuals with ASD to select interviewees. However, the organization requires compliance with its policies before sharing information with third parties. After a month of gathering and submitting the necessary documents, the organization replied with the same response. As a result, the schedule was adjusted, and the selection of interviewees shifted to contacting willing participants in online group communities via a social media platform instead.
- Despite contacting possible interviewees via online group communities, some respondents who had answered the preliminary survey were unavailable due to scheduling conflicts.
- Although it was part of the initial plan to provide insights and evaluate the entire output to enhance the documentary's credibility and ensure the accuracy of the information provided by interviewees, the timeframe for contacting a specialist was unattainable due to time constraints and scheduling conflicts.

5.1.3. Recommendations

- Sticking with the most minimalist style while envisioning the documentary flow could help future works easily modify or adjust the graphics if there are production and post-production changes.
- Future content producers should expect the unexpected and have a backup plan before writing the script or doing the interviews.
- Contact the interviewees immediately to allow them time to adjust and fit the interview into their schedules, as schedule conflicts are inevitable for parents. Other factors, such as their location, should also be considered.
- When planning similar projects or documentaries, it is also highly recommended to interview or consult an ASD specialist for credibility and accuracy. Give them a briefing about the project and schedule beforehand since most have a tight schedule.

5.2. Production

The production phase involved filming interviews and other footage needed for the video documentary.

5.2.1. Video Recording

Consent forms were sent to the interviewees through a social media messaging platform before video recording the interviews. These forms include the project's purpose and procedures, a list of items that the interviewees grant permission to, their signatures, and the date they signed. The video documentary producer ensures that the interviewees read and understand all three pages of the form and acknowledge

questions before signing the forms. This step is crucial before the filming of interviews and must be noted by all future content creators.

In the first interview, the video documentary producer faced no challenges because she was already familiar with the interview, and the place was nearby. However, she sought assistance from her peers for the second interview since she was unfamiliar with the location. The interviewee agreed and was informed beforehand that the documentary video producer and her peers would be joining her for the interview. For the third interview, the interviewee did not agree to film at her house, which led the video documentary producer to rent an area near her home. However, the producer was alone in this interview, and the location was a bit far. She realized seeking help was a wise decision in the second interview—especially when commuting with production equipment like a camera and tripod. Fortunately, the fourth interviewee requested to be interviewed at the first filming location, the first interviewee's house. The video producer had no issues with the venue. However, heavy rains made the commute challenging during that time, especially since the equipment was nearly soaked.

5.2.2. Challenges

- The documentary initially aims to present parents' experiences from various perspectives, including mothers and fathers. However, the respondents who participated in the preliminary survey were exclusively mothers.
- Commuting while carrying equipment could be a struggle.
- Heavy rainfall caused inconvenience during the fourth interview's filming.

5.2.3. Recommendations

- If possible, include perspectives from fathers of children diagnosed with ASD. Most documentaries, including this one, only focus on mothers' experiences. Hearing from the '*haligi ng tahanan*' or the father's side would offer a refreshing take on how they balance life and navigate challenges.
- When planning interviews, it is vital to consider the accessibility of respondents' locations. Before the actual interview, familiarize yourself with the area and make sure to have a guide on how to get there.
- Stay prepared for unpredictable weather conditions, especially during the rainy season. Handle your equipment with care, as it can be fragile.
- Before video recording, ensure the interviewees read, understand, and sign the consent forms. They must be fully aware of what might appear in the documentary video and where it will be publicly posted, especially if the objective of the documentary is to release and distribute it online.
- When interviewing respondents, it is crucial to understand the topic beforehand. Before interviewing them, make them feel comfortable by asking them how they are doing, talking about the inspirations behind the documentary, or even telling them stories about the journey before arriving at the place. Listen attentively to their answers to formulate follow-up questions and allow them time to finish their responses. Avoid interrupting or immediately asking follow-up questions while they're speaking. Sometimes, respondents pause to organize their ideas or spontaneously share new insights.

5.3. Post-production

The post-production phase focused on editing the interviews, incorporating graphics and text, polishing the documentary, and transcribing the interviews for closed captions.

5.3.1. Editing and Finalization

During the second and fourth interviews, technical challenges emerged. Since no enclosed area or room was available for filming during the second interview, audio issues and unexpected cuts occurred because one of the interviewee's children unintentionally moved the camera in its place. The presence of videos playing on a phone and amplified neighbors' music contributed to the audio issues during the interview. In the fourth interview, audio problems persisted due to heavy rainfall, phone rings, and audible dog barks—factors beyond the video producer's control.

All four interviewees assessed the final output through Google Forms and rated the documentary video an overall 10 out of 10, indicating excellence. While only one interviewee gave the script a 4 out of 5 rating, all participants rated the documentary video's script, content, organization, audio, graphics, quality, and creativity with a perfect 5 out of 5. In the suggestions or feedback section, only two interviewees indicated their remarks:

“Ang ganda ng pagka edit sa video”

“Wala naman ako any suggestions, ang masasabi kong napakalinaw at maayos ang gustong iparating sa mga manonood at Kung ano ang topic, at Sana may malaking maitulong nito bilang awareness sa mga tao o magulang na may anak, kamag-anak na may ASD o sa mga taong hindi nakakaintindi ng ano nga ba nga ang ASD? Hindi pa ako nakaka umpisa nangingilid na ang

aking luha at ramdam ko sa aming bawat nanay ang mga struggle, hirap, at saya na mga ginagawa namin at sa mga darating na pagsubok. Maraming salamat sa iyo at isa kaming naging topic mo, kaming may mga anak na ganito ang situation 😊”

Reading their comments was a heartwarming experience and made all the efforts poured into this production worthwhile.

5.3.2. Challenges

- During the video review before editing, one of the interviewees unexpectedly disclosed a private matter that may not have been intended for public sharing. The video producer noticed this scene and sought confirmation from her adviser and the interviewee regarding its inclusion. The interviewee disapproved of the inclusion, and the scene was edited out of the interview.
- Given that the video documentary producer worked with minimal equipment, some interviews had noticeable background noise. Unfortunately, using a lavalier microphone was not sufficient to reduce the noise.
- Editing was the most time-consuming task during the post-production phase. Due to the computer's capacity, rendering the documentary video took approximately 12 hours—equivalent to half a day. Specifically, the desktop lacked the recommended graphics card and sufficient storage capacity for efficient editing.
- The documentary video only employed a minimalist approach, using text on a black screen without any background video to avoid clutter in each scene. Due to time constraints, filming additional content as background videos for the introduction and end scenes was not achieved.

5.3.3. Recommendations

- Future content creators must be mindful of every scene in the interview and always seek permission when uncertain. Since interviews mostly consist of open-ended questions, cases like these are inevitable.
- With the technical aspects, making a video documentary also means investing in quality equipment to prevent problems in audio and video recording or editing the video documentary. A camera, lavalier microphone, and tripod are starters, but having a budget for production equipment improves the overall quality of the output.
- When working on post-production, it is also essential to consider the recommended computer specifications for editing, ensuring a smoother performance throughout the process.
- Planning to film footage outdoors should also have an allotted time in the schedule.
- Observing and watching how other documentaries are produced can significantly contribute to the overall production of your project.

The video documentary highlighted the experiences and coping strategies of mothers raising autistic children. Diagnoses can occur at various ages, and early recognition of signs helps prepare for interventions such as speech and occupational therapies. A Developmental Pediatrician typically handles diagnoses and therapy recommendations, though this can be costly for low- to middle-income families. Parents also face educational and social challenges. Special Education schools can help mitigate bullying, whereas regular schools might increase the risk. Public meltdowns can attract judgment and offensive comments, reflecting a lack of awareness about ASD. Balancing work and family life is difficult, requiring careful

scheduling. Initial denial is common, but acceptance is crucial. Autism, influenced by various factors, is a lifelong aspect of identity rather than a condition to be cured.

Creating the documentary was a fulfilling experience despite being a one-person production. The project encountered numerous obstacles from planning to execution but ultimately achieved its goal. The insights and recommendations from this process will benefit future documentary producers, helping ensure a smoother and more efficient production.

Special thanks go to those who supported and assisted with this video. Meeting the interviewees, hearing their stories, and gaining new perspectives was truly eye-opening.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Preliminary Survey via Google Forms

Preliminary Survey for "Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child"

Greetings!

I am Angela Marie Lumaguip, a 4th-year multimedia student at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU). I'm conducting a preliminary survey for my special project or undergraduate thesis entitled "**Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child**." This initial survey would greatly help me to choose and consider **four (4) working parents residing within Metro Manila who are willing to share their experiences in knowing and caring for their children diagnosed with ASD.**

Filipino will be the primary language used throughout the interview, which includes the questions to be asked. The search for interviewees will only be until the end of April, while the shoot will run for two months, from May to June 2024.

To ensure transparency and ethical standards, I will provide the selected participants with consent forms outlining the purpose of the documentary, the topics to be discussed, and their rights as interviewees before the agreed shoot.

If you have any questions or need clarification, please feel free to contact me via my university email: aslumaguip@upo.edu.ph.

*Ako po si Angela Marie Lumaguip, isang 4th-year multimedia student mula sa UP Open University. Ako po ay nagsasagawa ng maikling survey para sa aking special project o undergraduate thesis na pinamagatang "Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child." Sa pamamagitan ng pagsagot sa aking maikling survey, pipili po ako ng **apat (4) na nagtatrabahang magulang na naninirahan sa Metro Manila na handang magbahagi ng kanilang mga karanasan sa pag-alam at pag-aalaga sa kanilang mga anak na na-diagnose na may ASD.***

2. Participating in this short survey is purely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw from the survey at any time.

In compliance with R.A. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, rest assured that your privacy will be protected and all information, including personal and sensitive information, that you will provide will be handled with utmost confidentiality. Moreover, the data collected will not be distributed to third parties and will only be used for research purposes.

By completing this survey, you are consenting to participate and have your data used for this purpose.

Ang pagsagot mo sa maikling survey na ito ay boluntaryo, at may karapatan kang lumahok o hindi. Maaari ka ring umurong sa pagsagot anumang oras.

Bilang pagsunod sa R.A. 10173 o ang Data Privacy Act of 2012, makatitayak na ang iyong pagkakakilanlan ay mapaprotektahan at lahat ng impormasyon, kabilang ang personal at sensitibong impormasyon, na iyong ibibigay ay mananatiling pribado at kumpidensyal. Bukod dito, hindi ipapamahagi sa mga ikatlong partido ang mga nakuhang datos at gagamitin lamang ang mga ito para sa layunin ng pananaliksik.

Sa pagsagot ng survey na ito, pumapayag kang lumahok at gamitin ang iyong datos para sa layuning ito.

Mark only one oval.

- I agree
 I disagree

Demographic Profile

Filipino po ang magiging pangunahing wikang gagamitin sa buong interview. Ang paghahanap para sa mga makakapanayam ay hanggang sa katapusan ng Abril lamang, habang ang shoot ay tatagal naman po ng dalawang buwan, mula Mayo hanggang Hunyo 2024.

Upang masigurado ang kaligtasan at alinsunod sa ethical standards, bibigyan ko po ang mga mapipili ng consent forms kung saan nakabalangkas ang layunin ng dokumentaryo, mga paksa ng tatalakayin, at ang kanilang mga karapatan bilang mga kinakapanayam bago ang napagkasunduang shoot.

Kung mayroon ka pong anumang mga katanungan o kailangan ng paglilinaw, mangyaring huwag mag-atubiling makipag-ugnayan sa akin sa pamamagitan ng aking email sa unibersidad: aslumaguip@upo.edu.ph.

** indicates required question*

1. **Email ***

3. **Name ***

Pangalan

4. **Residence/Location ***

Please follow the format: Town, City (e.g. Fairview, Quezon City)

**I will only consider those within Metro Manila*

Tirahan/Lokasyon

Mangyaring sundin ang format: Bayan, Lungsod (hal. Fairview, Quezon City)

**Ako'y pipili lamang ng mga nakatira sa loob ng Metro Manila*

5. **Civil Status ***

Katayuang Sibil

Mark only one oval.

- Single Parent
 Married
 Widowed
 Separated
 Other: _____

6. **Occupation ***

Hanapbuhay/Trabaho

7. **Child's Age and Diagnosis ***

Edad ng anak at Diagnosis

8. **FB Link to contact/reach you ***

9. **Other ways to contact/reach you**

In case you're one of the selected interviewees, you may provide other messaging/communication platforms or other contact information that I may use to reach you.

*Iba pang mga paraan upang makipag-ugnayan sa'yo
Kung sakaling isa ka sa mga napiling makakapanayam, maaari kang magbigay ng iba pang mga plataporma ng pagmemensahe o komunikasyon na maaari kong gamitin upang makausap ko kayo.*

10. **Availability ***

Please state the time you're usually free/available and whether you're available on Weekends or Weekdays

Pakilagay ang oras na karaniwan kang walang ginagawa at kung available ka ng Weekends o Weekdays

13. Do you have some advice for your fellow parents who are in the early stages of discovering their child's diagnosis and may be unaware of what to do and not to do regarding caring for their child with ASD?

Mayroon po ba kayong maipapayo para sa inyong mga kapwa magulang na nasa maagang yugto ng pagtuklas ng diagnosis ng kanilang anak at maaaring hindi alam kung ano ang dapat gawin at hindi dapat gawin tungkol sa pag-aalaga sa kanilang anak na may ASD?

14. What prompted you to be featured or be a part of the documentary? (It* could be about your personal experiences, family's situation or needs)

Ano po ang nag-udyok sainyo na maging bahagi ng dokumentaryong ito? (Maaaring ito ay tungkol sa inyong mga personal na karanasan, sitwasyon o pangangailangan ng inyong pamilya)

Preliminary Survey

This short survey will only serve as a preliminary survey that would help me to determine/identify who I'll consider interviewing for the documentary.

Ang maikling survey na ito ay magsisihi lamang bilang isang paunang survey na makakatulong sa akin upang matukoy ko ang mga kinakapanayam na maaaring maging bahagi ng aking dokumentaryo.

11. Does your child undergo early interventions (therapies, etc.)? *

Sumasailalim po ba ang inyong anak sa mga maagang interbensyon (mga therapy, atbp.)?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

12. Are you well aware of each intervention/therapy your child currently receives? *

May malalim na pag-unawa po ba kayo sa bawat interbensyon/therapy na kasalukuyang natatanggap ng inyong anak?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Selected interviewees will be contacted via the information they gave and will be presented with consent forms before the actual interview.

Thank you for your efforts in participating in this short survey and helping me with my special project! I'm looking forward to getting to know and work with you all!

Ang mga mapipiling kinapanayam ay kakausapin sa pamamagitan ng impormasyong ibinigay nila at ipapakita ang mga consent form bago ang aktwal interview.

Salamat sa inyong pagsisikap sa paglahok sa maikling survey na ito at pagtulon sa akin sa aking special project! Inaasahan kong lubusan ko kayong makilala at makatrabaho!

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

APPENDIX B

Video Documentary Outline

Outline for the Special Project: Video Documentary

Title: Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child

Target duration length: 15-20 mins.

Language: Filipino

Objectives of the special project

The video documentary aims to

- To raise awareness among the parents who might be in the early stages of discovering their child's diagnosis and may be unaware of it.
- To present the real-life challenges of families with family member/ members diagnosed with ASD to debunk myths or misconceptions about ASD.
- To mitigate the public stigma and discrimination associated with ASD.
- To promote inclusivity and ASD empowerment by disseminating and sharing the output or content material to various social media platforms.

Outline:

I. Black screen

a. Statistics on Filipinos diagnosed with ASD

- "One in every 100 Filipinos has ASD, representing a total of around 1.2 million people in the Philippines." (Autism Society Philippines)
- "Numerous studies have shown that parents of autistic children struggle with daily challenges encompassing medical, financial, educational, and social aspects."
- "How far can a parent's love go?"

II. Title screen

- Faces of parents
- "4 Families, 4 Different Perspectives"
- "Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child"

III. Interviews

a. Lower thirds: Parent's name (if parent will allow) and child's age

b. In-between shots

- i. Montage of a day in their lives (if frontal shots will not be allowed, back and side shots only)
- ii. Montage of their child with ASD doing their hobbies (if frontal shots will not be allowed, back and side shots only)

Questions to be asked for the Interview (Q&A's primary language would be Filipino, but will still include optional English subtitles in closed captions to make it accessible to other nationalities)

- a. *Ipakilala ang inyong sarili: pangalan, trabaho, ilang taon na ang inyong anak.*
(Please introduce yourself: name, work, child's age)
- b. *Anong edad ng inyong anak nang ma-diagnose sya na may ASD?*
(At what age did your child get diagnosed with ASD?)
- c. *Anu-ano po yung signs or symptoms na nakita nyo sa inyong anak na sa tingin nyo ay kakaiba sa ibang mga bata na ka-edad nya?*
(What are the signs or symptoms you've seen in your child that make them different from other children their age?)
- d. *Anong edad ng inyong anak ng ito ay pinatingnan nyo sa isang espesyalista?*
(At what age did your child get checked by a specialist?)
- e. *Ano o sino ang nagconvince sa inyo ipa-check sa espesyalista ang inyong anak?*
(What or who convinced you to bring your child to a specialist?)
- f. *Ano yung mga tanong o concerns na pumasok sa isip nyo noong sinabi ng espesyalista ang kanyang diagnosis sa inyong anak?*
(Are there questions or concerns that made you think when the specialist told you about the diagnosis of your child?)
- g. *Ano ang nakatulong sa inyong mag-asawa o pamilya na matanggap (or acceptance) yung sitwasyon ng inyong anak?*
(What helped your family accept the situation with your child?)
- h. *Mayroon po bang interventions na ginagawa sa inyong anak? Sino po ang nagprescribe ng intervention?*
(Does your child undergo interventions? Who prescribed the intervention?)
- i. *Anu-ano po ang intervention na sumasailalim ang inyong anak? Maaari po bang ipaliwanag ang bawat isang intervention kung paano ginagawa o ano ang mga kinakailangan?*
(What kind of interventions does your child undergo? Can you please explain how each intervention works or what requirements are needed?)
- j. *Sa bawat isang intervention na sumasailalim ang inyong anak, ano po ang mga hamon o pagsubok na naranasan at nararanasan ninyo?*
(With every intervention your child undergoes, what are the challenges or issues you've experienced or are currently facing?)
- k. *Bilang magulang na may anak na may ASD, ano pong mga espesyal na bagay o katangian ang napansin mo sa kanya na hindi nakikita sa karaniwang bata?*
(As a parent of a child with ASD, what are some unique traits you've noticed with your child that are not seen in a usual child?)
- l. *Anu-ano ang mga hamon o pagsubok na inyong naranasan at nararanasan na may kinalaman sa pag-aaral ng isang batang may ASD? (i.e. paghahanap ng paaralan, tuition fee, etc.).*

(What are some challenges or issues you've faced or are currently experiencing that are associated with the education of a child with ASD? (i.e., finding a school, paying tuition fees, etc.)

- m. *Paano nyo po ito binigyan ng solusyon?*
(How do you solve these?)
- n. *Anu-ano ang mga challenges or issue na inyong naranasan at nararanasan na may kinalaman sa reaksyon/pakikisalamuha ng publiko sa batang may ASD? (i.e. stigma, mga paniniwala at assumptions ng mga tao sa inyong paligid tungkol sa ASD)*
(What are some challenges or issues you've faced or are currently experiencing related to the public's reaction/interaction with a child with ASD?)
- o. *Paano nyo po ito binigyan ng solusyon?*
(How do you solve these?)
- p. *Paano po ninyo nababalanse ang pagtatrabaho at pagiging magulang na may anak na na-diagnose na may ASD?*
(How do you balance your career and life in general as a parent of a child diagnosed with ASD?)
- Follow up: *May mabibigay po ba kayong mga payo sa kapwa ninyong magulang na ngayon palang nalalaman ang diagnosis ng kanilang anak at mga do's and don't's bilang magulang?*
(Do you have some advice for your fellow parents who are in the early stages of discovering their child's diagnosis and may be unaware of what to do and not to do regarding caring for their child with ASD?)
- q. *Kung may hiling po kayo o aksyon na maitutulong ng gobyerno ukol sa ASD, ano po ang inyong hihilingin?*
(If you have a request or action that the government can help with ASD, what would you request?)
- r. *Kung ako po'y isang ordinaryong taong walang kaalam-alam kung ano ang ASD, paano po ninyo ipapaliwanag sa akin ito at imumulat ang karamihan tungkol dito?*
(If I'm an ordinary person who doesn't have an idea or a clue about what ASD is, how can you explain it to me and educate and raise awareness among people about it?)

IV. Closing/End Credits

- a. Crew
- b. Special thanks/Acknowledgments
- c. Music used

APPENDIX C

Consent Forms

Cover Page

CONSENT FORM FOR THE SPECIAL PROJECT

“Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with a Child on Autism Spectrum.”

Here is the complete information about the special project. Please read thoroughly and supply the information needed for this special project. By signing this consent form, you agree, understand, and consent to be part of this interview and video production.

Introduction

I am Angela Marie Lumaguip, a fourth-year multimedia student at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU). I am currently working on a video documentary project titled *“Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with a Child on Autism Spectrum.”* Due to the lack of media representation of ASD in documentary films, one of the project goals is to release it to the public and distribute it on various social media platforms like YouTube and Facebook. Apart from disseminating the documentary film publicly, this project would be significant in raising awareness and giving voice to parents with children diagnosed with ASD towards an inclusive society.

Purpose of the Project

The project aims to help develop inclusivity in our society regarding Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Specifically, the documentary project aims to:

- Give viewers a broad understanding of autism and promote inclusivity in our society by debunking myths or misconceptions and mitigating public stigma and discrimination associated with ASD.
- Raise awareness and help parents who might be in the early stages of discovering their child's diagnosis and may be unaware of what to do and not to do regarding caring for their child with ASD.
- Present the real-life challenges of families with family members diagnosed with ASD.

Procedures

If you agree to be part of this project, the interview will be recorded in video and will be scheduled according to the interviewee's availability from June to July 2024. It will be one hour or may exceed that, depending on the answers provided. Filipino will be the primary language used throughout the interview, which includes the questions to be asked. The location of the shoot depends on the agreed-upon place between the interviewee and the interviewer.

First Interviewee (1 of 2)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM TO BE INTERVIEWED ON FILM

I, _____ (state your name), hereby grant permission to be a part of this documentary film titled "Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child," to (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Photograph
- Video record
- Record my voice
- Upload images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)
- Photograph my child
- Video record my child
- Record my child's voice
- Upload my child's images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)

For the purpose/s of (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Uploading the material/s indicated above as open educational resource/s in the UPOU Networks website (networks.upou.edu.ph) and UPOU Networks Social Media sites, whether or not for gain, with or without monetization.
- Using the material/s as an open educational resource/s for UPOU courses.
- Sharing the materials online as an open educational resource/s with various learners from different institutions.
- Keeping the recording for documentation purposes.

By permitting the interviewer and their authorized representatives to perform any of the above activities, I understand and agree that the following pieces of personal and sensitive personal information, as defined in Republic Act No. 10173 ("Data Privacy Act of 2012"), shall likewise be processed by UPOU:

1. Full Name
2. Child's Age and Diagnosis
3. Civil Status
4. Occupation

I allow the interviewer the right to (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Reproduce
- Keep on record
- Exhibit/display
- Broadcast/distribute
- Create derivative works of these images and recordings in any media now known or later developed.

First Interviewee (2 of 2)

I agree and understand that my personal information may be processed both by way of computer media and on paper in compliance with the rules on data protection, including those relating to data security.

I understand that my participation in this filmed interview involves answering the questions of the interviewer, and I will be recorded throughout the interview. I also understand that my participation is purely voluntary and that I have the right to withdraw without giving a reason and without being penalized or disadvantaged. I acknowledge that there is no compensation for my participation and that I have no further claims against any individual involved in this production.

Should I have any questions or concerns about my personal information, I may address them to:

Name of Interviewer: Angela Marie S. Lumaguip

E-mail: aslumaguip@up.edu.ph

Contact No.: 09760284018

I consent voluntarily to participate in this project and further attest that I have read this consent form and fully understand its contents.

Printed Name and Signature

JUNE 15, 2024

Date

Conducted by:

Angela Marie S. Lumaguip
Researcher/Interviewer

Date of video recording: JUNE 15, 2024

Venue of video recording: NOVALICHES, QUEZON CITY

Video recording done by: ANGELA MARIE LUMAGUIP

Second Interviewee (1 of 2)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM TO BE INTERVIEWED ON FILM

I, [REDACTED] (state your name), hereby grant permission to be a part of this documentary film titled "Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child," to (put a check on the appropriate box):

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- Video record
- Record my voice
- Upload images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)
- Photograph my child
- Video record my child
- Record my child's voice
- Upload my child's images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)

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- Keep on record
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- Broadcast/distribute
- Create derivative works of these images and recordings in any media now known or later developed.

Second Interviewee (2 of 2)

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Should I have any questions or concerns about my personal information, I may address them to:

Name of Interviewer: Angela Marie S. Lumaguip

E-mail: aslumaguip@up.edu.ph

Contact No.: 09760284018

I consent voluntarily to participate in this project and further attest that I have read this consent form and fully understand its contents.

Printed Name and Signature

June 30, 2024

Date

Conducted by:

Angela Marie S. Lumaguip
Researcher/Interviewer

Date of video recording: JUNE 30, 2024

Venue of video recording: BIGNAY, VALENZUELA

Video recording done by: ANGELA LUMAGUIP

Third Interviewee (1 of 2)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM TO BE INTERVIEWED ON FILM

I, [REDACTED] (state your name), hereby grant permission to be a part of this documentary film titled "**Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child,**" to (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Photograph
- Video record
- Record my voice
- Upload images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)
- Photograph my child
- Video record my child
- Record my child's voice
- Upload my child's images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)

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1. Full Name
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3. Civil Status
4. Occupation

I allow the interviewer the right to (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Reproduce
- Keep on record
- Exhibit/display
- Broadcast/distribute
- Create derivative works of these images and recordings in any media now known or later developed.

Third Interviewee (2 of 2)

I agree and understand that my personal information may be processed both by way of computer media and on paper in compliance with the rules on data protection, including those relating to data security.

I understand that my participation in this filmed interview involves answering the questions of the interviewer, and I will be recorded throughout the interview. I also understand that my participation is purely voluntary and that I have the right to withdraw without giving a reason and without being penalized or disadvantaged. I acknowledge that there is no compensation for my participation and that I have no further claims against any individual involved in this production.

Should I have any questions or concerns about my personal information, I may address them to:

Name of Interviewer: Angela Marie S. Lumaguip

E-mail: aslumaguip@up.edu.ph

Contact No.: 09760284018

I consent voluntarily to participate in this project and further attest that I have read this consent form and fully understand its contents.

Printed Name and Signature

7/12/2024

Date

Conducted by:

Angela Marie S. Lumaguip
Researcher/Interviewer

Date of video recording: JULY 12, 2024

Venue of video recording: RECTO, MANILA

Video recording done by: ANGELA MARIE LUMAGUIP

Fourth Interviewee (1 of 2)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM TO BE INTERVIEWED ON FILM

I, [REDACTED] (state your name), hereby grant permission to be a part of this documentary film titled "**Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child,**" to (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Photograph
- Video record
- Record my voice
- Upload images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)
- Photograph my child
- Video record my child
- Record my child's voice
- Upload my child's images/audio/videos/photographs to the UPOU Networks and its social media sites (i.e. YouTube, Facebook, etc.)

For the purpose/s of (put a check on the appropriate box):

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- Using the material/s as an open educational resource/s for UPOU courses.
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1. Full Name
2. Child's Age and Diagnosis
3. Civil Status
4. Occupation

I allow the interviewer the right to (put a check on the appropriate box):

- Reproduce
- Keep on record
- Exhibit/display
- Broadcast/distribute
- Create derivative works of these images and recordings in any media now known or later developed.

Fourth Interviewee (2 of 2)

I agree and understand that my personal information may be processed both by way of computer media and on paper in compliance with the rules on data protection, including those relating to data security.

I understand that my participation in this filmed interview involves answering the questions of the interviewer, and I will be recorded throughout the interview. I also understand that my participation is purely voluntary and that I have the right to withdraw without giving a reason and without being penalized or disadvantaged. I acknowledge that there is no compensation for my participation and that I have no further claims against any individual involved in this production.

Should I have any questions or concerns about my personal information, I may address them to:

Name of Interviewer: Angela Marie S. Lumaguip

E-mail: aslumaguip@up.edu.ph

Contact No.: 09760284018

I consent voluntarily to participate in this project and further attest that I have read this consent form and fully understand its contents.

Printed Name and Signature

July 23, 2024
Date

Conducted by:

Angela Marie S. Lumaguip
Researcher/Interviewer

Date of video recording: JULY 23, 2024
Venue of video recording: NOVALICHES, QUEZON CITY
Video recording done by: ANGELA MARIE LUMAGUIP

APPENDIX D

Documentary Video Feedback Form

Overall Rating for the Final Video

On a scale of 1 to 10, 1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest, how would you rate the overall video?

4 responses

Comments/Suggestions/Feedback

Feel free to add any suggestions, improvements or message to me! :)

4 responses

N/A

Ang ganda ng pagka edit sa vedio

na

Wala naman ako any suggestions,ang masasabi klng napakalinaw at maayos ang gustong ipa rating sa mga manonood at Kung ano ang topic,at Sana malaking maitulong ito bilang awareness sa mga tao o magulang na may anak,kamagnaak na may ASD o sa mga taong hindi nakakaintindi na ano nga ba nga ba ang ASD?hindi pa ako nakakaumpisa nangingilid na ang aking luha at ramdam ko sa aming bawat nanay ang mga struggle,hirap at Saya na mga Nagagawa namin at sa mga darating na pagsubok.maraming salmat sayo at isa kaming naging topic mo kaming mga may anak na ganito ang situation 😊

Evaluation Form

APPENDIX E

The Documentary Video

[Living in Two Worlds: A Documentary on Balancing Life with an Autistic Child](#)

APPENDIX F

The Highlights of the Interviews

This section contains the summarized discussions with four (4) interviewees that were recorded on video.

First Interviewee

The first interviewee is the interviewer's aunt, a government employee from Novaliches, Quezon City. Her son is eight (8) years old and was diagnosed with Asperger's syndrome when he was two (2) years old. At the same age, she began seeking help from her husband's aunt, who is working at a health center and referred them to consult a Developmental Pediatrician (DevPed) after noticing signs like constant tiptoeing, arranging objects in lines, lack of eye contact, and unresponsiveness when called. With the help of her mother, siblings, mother-in-law, and her husband's aunt, she was encouraged to get her child checked by a specialist.

After her child was diagnosed with ASD, she asked her doctor if it was genetic or if she was sick during pregnancy, but the doctor replied that there was no specific explanation of its causes until now. Despite hearing the diagnosis, they need to accept the situation, help each other, and provide their child with therapies or interventions that he needs.

The DevPed prescribed therapies or interventions for their child, including occupational therapy (OT), speech therapy, and behavior therapy. OT helps him learn to handle a spoon and other activities to improve his motor skills. Speech therapy addresses his echolalia, where he repeats words. Behavior therapy assists with his social and communication skills, particularly his sensitivity to loud noises and laughter.

These therapies or interventions do not have any requirements. They would only be determined through the DevPed's assessment and suggestions.

She also discussed her challenges during each intervention and the following improvements. Before OT, her child had difficulties wearing clothes and shoes. At four (4), he could already wear them by himself and eat without assistance. His echolalia also lessened after undergoing speech therapy. Although he just recently started behavior therapy, they were hopeful of seeing improvements in the future.

When asked what unique traits she noticed that are not seen in a typical or neurotypical child, she was amazed by her child's ability to read at the age of one (1). By age two (2), he could already read a whole toddler book and memorize lullaby or nursery rhymes. Growing up, he loved to sing, and the first song he memorized was *"Ikaw at Ako"* by Moira Dela Torre when he was three (3) years old.

She mentioned enrolling her child in a SpEd at Kaligayahan Elementary School. While she has not faced any challenges yet and hopes to avoid them, there is a possibility that she will face potential issues like discrimination and bullying. If it happened, they would find a way to handle it. In the social context, she highlighted the lack of awareness and understanding about individuals diagnosed with ASD. Some people mistakenly label ASD as a mental disorder or disease, but it is actually a broad-spectrum condition or neurodevelopmental disability. She also mentioned how people would stare when her child had tantrums or meltdowns in public. Following the therapist's advice, they would ignore them and let their child be for a while unless it came to a point where he would start hurting himself. The more they are forced, the more likely they will throw tantrums.

- *"Wala lang, hinahayaan lang namin [people staring at them] dahil wala naman silang ano d'on eh— kontribusyon sa amin."*

Balancing work as a government employee and being a mother of a child diagnosed with ASD is very challenging. As a family, they prioritize their responsibilities, care for themselves, and organize their schedules for family bonding, like jogging and walking. Exposing the child outside or to a new environment allows them to adapt and socialize with others. She also encouraged fellow parents to communicate with their children often, which should be a priority. They should also have playtime, understand, and allot time for their children.

She also expressed that the government should allocate funds for those who could not afford therapy sessions, establish affordable therapy centers or institutions, and campaign for awareness or advocacy for those with special needs. The interview ended with the statement that she would raise awareness and educate others about ASD by explaining it to them and having a deeper understanding of the condition regardless of age.

Second Interviewee

The second interviewee resides in Valenzuela and is a 38-year-old mother of three children, ages 5, 8, and 10, all diagnosed with ASD. She is a housewife focusing on caring for their children, while her husband works in construction as a foreman. Her eldest was diagnosed with intellectual impairment at five (5) years old, the same age as her middle child, who was diagnosed with mild autism. Meanwhile, the youngest child was diagnosed with moderate autism when he was two (2) years old, wherein he exhibits speech delay and non-verbal communication.

When the eldest child was four (4) years old, she observed that he was very playful but unresponsive when called. They often stayed indoors to prevent him from potentially hurting other children while playing outside. Due to insufficient funds and a

neighbor's suggestion that he might just be a late bloomer, they delayed scheduling a check-up. On the other hand, when the second child was between two and three years old, she showed no signs of autism. However, signs began to appear when she turned five (5), prompting her to request an assessment from the doctor. She also noticed that the third child lacked eye contact, convincing the couple to have the child checked by a SpEd doctor. Despite the pandemic, they saved money to have their children assessed.

- *“Naiyak nga ‘ko sa doktor n’on, eh, Kasi nga, bakit naman ganon? Tatlo talaga yung anak ko na may... autism. Sobrang hirap din pala ang ganyang kondisyon ng isang bata.”*
- *“Hindi naman ‘yan siya sakit, eh. Hindi ko na iniisip yung... mga struggle... sa autism, pero ‘yun pala napakahirap din pala. Hindi biro magkaroon ng anak na ganyan.”*

Upon hearing the diagnoses, the second interviewee's first concern was how their family would meet their children's needs, given their financial constraints. Fortunately, Valenzuela offers a once-a-week free therapy program that helps them manage financially. She also expressed gratitude to online communities, particularly Autism PH, and fellow parents for their advice, which helped her accept and understand her children's situation.

According to their doctor, all three of her children require occupational therapy, speech therapy, and Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA). Although this was the case, only one of their children can receive ABA due to lack of budget. Sometimes, she applies therapy at home by training and teaching them to be independent— doing household chores, taking a bath alone, or wearing their clothes on their own. She also expressed how they are having difficulty with constant therapies since they cannot

afford them. They only depend on the free therapy program provided by their local government unit. If only they could afford it, they would be more than willing to pay for their therapy sessions. She also mentioned that a session per hour costs Php 800.

- *“Eh, kung may kakayahan lang po ako mag therapy, ako na lang po mag-ano e— magbayad. Eh, wala eh.”*

Among her three children, the second child stands out with many unique traits not typically seen in other children. Although she struggles with writing due to a weak grip on pencils, she excels in memorization, spelling, reading, and Mathematics. She also mentioned that while the youngest was initially non-verbal, he started pronouncing some words. Despite her eldest having learning difficulties, he can already somehow manage errands independently.

All of them are currently enrolled in a SpEd school, and she hopes they can transfer to a regular school someday, especially the second child. However, she is concerned about the child’s behavior and the possibility of bullying, mainly due to her hyperactivity and short attention span. The second child is also the only one among her siblings receiving ABA therapy, which helps her adapt to her environment and the behavior of neurotypical children. As their parents, they need to help each other and give their best to provide for their children’s needs since they must learn how to be independent.

Shifting the focus to social context, she opened up some personal experiences that people would constantly question her children’s behavior and would always feel the need to explain her children’s condition to others or please them when they were having tantrums or meltdowns. Although online group communities about ASD already exist, she recalled a time years ago when awareness was still lacking. She felt some people would talk negatively about her family behind her back but were nice to her

face. Because of her child's actions, her neighbor jumped to conclusions and suggested enrolling them at a SpEd school even though she had not consulted a doctor or received a diagnosis yet. As a mother, she felt discriminated against and hurt by her neighbor's decisions ahead of her. Despite these uncontrollable situations, praying and having faith in the Lord remains her only solution.

Being a mother is already a challenging job. However, she strives to manage and balance everything by making a single trip to the market and teaching her children one by one so each can focus. She also advised her fellow parents going through the same situation to accept their child's situation, pay attention to their doctor's advice, and always pray and have faith in the Lord. Even though autism is a lifetime condition, she believes that receiving therapies is essential for them to become independent and capable of defending themselves in the future. She was inspired by the stories from her fellow parents about their children achieving independence. They focus not on their children's condition but on their skills and capabilities.

Aside from the free therapy program available in their area, interviewee number 2 hopes the government will hire more therapists specializing in ASD, as many parents like her are waiting for their turn to receive free therapy for their children. She voiced her concern that they have been waiting since 2019 and have only received free speech therapy once for her two children. She also wishes for sponsors and get-togethers for individuals with ASD during Autism Awareness Month in April. As the interview came to an end, she talked about how difficult it is for them as parents to control their children with ASD behavior whenever they are having meltdowns, which she hopes other people learn to accept and understand their condition.

Third Interviewee

The third interviewee is a mother from Manila who works as a call center supervisor and has a three-year-old (3) child. His son was diagnosed with ASD at two and a half (2 ½) years old. He did not receive a specific diagnosis, which is often misinterpreted, as levels are only assigned when individuals with ASD reach the appropriate age. At one year old, he could say 'mama' and 'papa,' but his development suddenly stopped at age two, becoming non-verbal and unresponsive when called.

As a mother, she closely observed her child's actions and development, noticing differences from her first child. It led her to research and eventually seek a check-up for her child. Initially, she was in denial, thinking her son might just be a late bloomer or misdiagnosed. Fortunately, she was financially able to provide for her son's needs, including follow-up check-ups, therapies, and consultations with their DevPed. She mentioned that unconditional love helped her accept her child's condition. For their family, they did not view it as a disability but instead saw him as a late learner with his own developmental pace.

They meet with their son's professional therapist once a week, every Monday. According to his DevPed, occupational therapy is the only recommended intervention for his age. She asked his therapist for suggested activities, like puzzles, to help him develop his motor skills even while at home. She also sought advice and ideas from online group communities that might apply to him.

Kai's sleep routine and tantrums were some of the challenges she faced. He would throw tantrums if he did not want to do what was asked of him. Thankfully, he somewhat overcame that behavior and now knows what to do when he feels uncomfortable. Others usually say that autistic individuals have their own strengths. Since he is currently only three (3) years old, she has not noticed any specific strengths

yet. However, she acknowledged his interest in music. She saw that he had downloaded a piano keyboard application on his tablet and could easily follow the notes on the screen.

Since the son has not started school yet, she shared some of the challenges she anticipates regarding his education. She thinks there would be no challenges if he were placed in a SpEd school, as they provide an exclusive environment for children like him and recognize his needs. However, her main concerns would be the possibility of bullying and being left out if he were recommended to transfer to a regular school.

When asked about her challenges in a social context, she mentioned that she has not experienced discrimination so far. However, if she ever did, she would ignore it and continue as if nothing had happened. She observed that her child does not throw tantrums in public but often starts clapping and jumping if he feels uncomfortable. Other relatives have even suggested that he is simply a late bloomer and questioned the accuracy of his diagnosis. Despite this, she believes in what would effectively help her child.

Balancing her schedules as a call center supervisor and a mother is challenging. Luckily, their schedules are well-aligned for taking care of their children. Her husband works from home, while her work hours are from 2 AM to 11 AM. She looks after Kai as soon as he wakes up and feeds him lunch until he sleeps in the afternoon. Her in-laws and siblings are also very helpful in looking after their children. She also advised fellow parents in similar situations that acceptance and early interventions are crucial. Some parents are still uncertain about their child's condition, leading them to delay the interventions that the child should already be receiving. She also shared her experience of waiting years before they could get assessed by a DevPed.

Consequently, she hopes that the government will increase the number of professionals specializing in ASD. When they went to the Philippine General Hospital (PGH), they had to wait three (3) years from the day they inquired about scheduling her child for an assessment. Due to this long wait, they switched to a private hospital, where they still had to wait a year. She empathizes with those who cannot afford private hospitals, as consultations and therapies are expensive. She also mentioned that therapy costs around Php 1,000 per session, but with a PWD ID, the cost is reduced to Php 960 per session—meanwhile, a session with their DevPed costs Php 6,000.

For her, educating and raising awareness about ASD among people could be difficult because many words can be used to express depending on the person you are talking to. However, she views ASD as not a disability. She believes that individuals with ASD simply have different abilities, their own developmental pace, and a unique perspective of the world. Due to a lack of awareness, some people describe them with other disorders or use insulting words without understanding their actual condition. She has faith that they can lead normal lives in the long run.

- *"Yung ASD is not a disability. Again, it's just happen na meron silang ibang ability, or ibang pace, ibang world."*

Fourth Interviewee

The fourth interviewee is also from Quezon City, the same as the first interviewee. She is an on-call pet groomer and a mother to a six-year-old (6) boy diagnosed at age five (5) with Autism Level 1 with speech and language impairment. He was three (3) years old when the pandemic began. During that time, she noticed some signs where he aligned toys and threw tantrums (banging his head, pulling his

hair, hurting himself) when he did not get what he wanted. They feared going to the hospital to consult a doctor about his signs because of the pandemic.

The mother often compared him to his siblings. She decided to get him checked because she noticed that her youngest child seemed more mature. Although she had suspicions, she wanted to hear directly from a specialist to confirm the diagnosis.

Also, in 2023, she attempted to enroll her son in Kindergarten but faced challenges because he would stay up late, causing them to skip school. She realized something was going on and decided to get him checked. Although she is already aware of such conditions, she scheduled an appointment at the Philippine Children's Medical Center (PCMC), where a neurodevelopmental doctor diagnosed him through screening tests and interviews. In addition, they consulted a private neurodevelopmental doctor, costing them Php 4,000, and confirmed the same diagnosis after a one-on-one assessment with her child.

The mother did not view it as a failure but as something they needed to address. She even asked the doctor if there was a cure for his condition, but the doctor explained that there was none, only therapy.

While they did not struggle much with caring for him, as he is not as hyperactive as some other autistic children, accepting the situation became easier through prayers and guidance from the Lord. Since they were not allowed to go outside during the pandemic, she started to expose him to different environments. She sometimes asked him to buy something for her, return borrowed items, or simply call for someone. Unlike the other interviewees who have sought interventions or therapies for their children, the child of the fourth interviewee has yet to receive any due to insufficient funds. However, the doctor recommended that he undergo occupational and speech therapies.

The child is sweet, obedient, and well-behaved. He is currently enrolled in a SpEd program at a nearby elementary school. Academically, his mother struggles with his difficulties in schoolwork. He can follow activities at school but only with the teacher's guidance. Sometimes, she helps him write his name, but he often loses concentration, so she lets him be. She would be surprised when he eventually completes it on his own. Despite his delayed development, he is creatively inclined. He excels at drawing, coloring, and building characters using clay or blocks, like robots.

During the pandemic, she was still in denial and felt embarrassed to take him with her outside. People would constantly compare him to other children his age and ask numerous questions about his development. She ignored them, feeling no need to explain or answer their questions. While neurotypical children attend morning classes, children with special needs are placed in the afternoon. Many parents at the same school were unaware of the afternoon SpEd program. Once, a parent from the same school asked where her child attended classes. When she replied that her child was in the afternoon SpEd program, the parent responded with an insulting remark about her child.

- *"Ta's sasabihin nila, "Saan kayo pumapasok?" "Diyang sa ano..." "Ba't hapon?" Do'n ko na lang sinabi sa kanila na, "Hindi, sa SpEd." "Ah, sa SpEd? Ano yan abnormal?" Sabi ko, "Grabe naman kayo, hindi naman. Kasi ganito..." Explain nanaman ako."*
- *"Minsan, meron pang sabi na, "Ay, diyang pumapasok sa mga ano, mga sira ulo?" Ini-ignore ko na rin 'yon, pero syempre masakit."*

Before, her son was afraid of people, including his playmates. Sometimes, he would push them away and prefer to be alone. She would struggle when they walked

because he would always cling to her. With her help in training him to adapt to his environment, he can now socialize with others, although he dislikes being teased by other children.

She also shared some myths people have told her about the cause of his condition, such as taking medicine, karma, or a curse. However, she did not believe these myths and consulted the doctor, who confirmed that there were still no specific causes of ASD.

Like the other interviewees, balancing her work as an on-call pet groomer and her role as a mother is very challenging. She only works on weekends and holidays when her children do not have classes. She cannot work daily because her three children would be left at home. Although she relies on her ten-year-old eldest child to look after his siblings, her child with ASD would skip meals if she were not around. Despite wanting to work regularly, she could not because no one would look after her autistic child. She advised parents in similar situations that acceptance is crucial. Even though it is difficult, parents should be the first to accept and adjust to the situation.

- *"Kung hindi kasi nila matanggap iyan, pa'no tatanggapin ng ibang tao?"*

They need to strive and do their best to provide for all their children's needs. However, she also reminded parents not to focus too much on one child, which might cause jealousy among the siblings. It is important to explain the situation and help their children understand.

She hopes the government will increase the number of specialists in the field, particularly neurodevelopmental pediatricians, as it took them a year to get a check-up appointment at PCMC. She also expressed that people like her, who had to borrow money for their child's check-up, should be able to afford consultations. Additionally, she wishes for more SpEd programs in public schools. It would be challenging for

parents to enroll their children if only a few public schools offer SpEd programs, for they cannot accommodate all children, leaving parents who cannot afford tuition fees with no choice but not to send their children to school. She also wanted a sustainable livelihood for parents who share her situation, making affordable therapies accessible to them. Although she mentioned that they applied for Kabahagi Center for Children with Disabilities last year, a Quezon City Local Government program initiative, they have not yet been called for a schedule.

Other people often blame parents when their children have meltdowns in public. Some might even take videos and post them on social media without understanding or knowing the real story. She emphasized that people need to be mindful of the parents' feelings and what they are going through by avoiding judgment and letting them be or ignoring them instead. Children with ASD have different fears and can be triggered by various things, leading to tantrums. At the same time, parents of autistic children should also consider their child's feelings, knowing that they cannot always keep up with neurotypical children. She also mentioned that people should always show respect by avoiding derogatory terms like "*abnoy*" and "*abnormal*" as much as possible, as these are hurtful to parents. No parent wants their child to be called such names.